

DYNAMICS OF TECHNICAL TRAINING OF 11-12 YEAR OLD TENNIS PLAYERS

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Abstract: This is it in the article young tennis player of girls' technical preparation dynamics universal and special tools using light up given. Research At the end of received results on the surface necessary instruction and recommendations statement done.

Key words: *young tennis players, technician readiness, quickness, means, physicality indicator.*

Sign in. Physical chance each one of an athlete movement from the activity come came out without differently assessment to all of us known. Young tennis player girls also try preparation dynamics where level that determination and our country honor authoritative in competitions worthy can protect athletes sorted get in order to young tennis player from girls universal and special tools using research practice organize done. Until us many scientists by one series our science research take went. Including: A. A Pulatov, Sh.A. Pulatov, S.K Abidov, F.A Pulatov and again many scientists researched young of tennis players physical preparation indicators determination and in them error and shortcomings eliminate reach in order to own their research take they went But it was passed research of work to many despite young tennis player of girls technical preparation during in them physical to downloads tolerance indicators, technical qualification by improving to go and adaptation elements enough by learning not issued. Young tennis player of girls technical preparation dynamics from our side organize done scientific research at work light up given.

Research Purpose: Age tennis player of girls' technical preparation dynamics universal and special tools using determination and efficiency indicators analysis to achieve.

Research skill: Young table tennis player of girls' technical preparation effectiveness improvement.

Organization of research methods: Scientific and methodical books analysis, mathematical-statistical analysis, pedagogical observation, pedagogical control, pedagogical testing.

Research results and discussion: In our country physical education and public of sports wide in order promote reached the bride and our president by

creating being given wide of possibilities used without young tennis player of girls movement preparation dynamics determination and in them shortcomings eliminate reach remedy events shaping equal to young sportsman of girls physical preparation level improvement by us in order to scientific research activity was conducted.

Exercises technique about concept pedagogical and biomechanics the point from the point of view open to be given can. Pedagogical the point literally, physically exercises technique is mobile of activities more efficient methods application is understood. Physical exercises technique regularly respectively in development will: used to technique improve, sometimes old techniques fades, the new one will come This is the process series conditions with related: sports training level requirements increased to go many improved methods search as a result, scientific research of work result and of importance increased in the course of teaching methodology in improvement, complex, but effective methods apply in the process, a new sports projectile to the body on arrival, ski of technique to be fulfilled correction the introduction necessity at birth and etc.

(Physical education theory and methodology. T.S.Usmonkhodjayev , O', Tursunov , Kh. Meloboyev. Tashkent 2008 p. 39).

Table 1
Young tennis player of girls' technical preparation dynamics indicators

T/r	Control test name		To Tk	TG	NG	t	p
1	A joke (times)	from the right	To Tk	14.3±1.7	15.1±1.3	0.15	<0.05
				19.5±1.4	17.9±1.5	2.24	>0.05
		from the left	To Tk	12.9±1.9	13.1±1.9	0.15	<0.05
				17.4±1.1	15.5±1.7	2.24	>0.05
2	Tennis ball cut transmission (times)		To Tk	5.4±1.8	6.1±1.89	0.15	<0.05
				8.1±1.09	7.6±1.64	2.24	>0.05
3	Top-spin shot perform (times)		To Tk	4.5±1.15	4.5±1.89	0.15	<0.05
				6.9±1.3	5.8±1.62	2.24	>0.05
4	From the left and from the right point (triangle)		To Tk	6.2±1.4	6.14±1.02	0.15	<0.05
				7.9±1.50	6.22±1.18	2.24	>0.05

Young tennis player of girls' special tools using preparation indicators where level that accuracy input in order to control test practices current done. Initial special our tool a joke the blow execution reaches through done increased. Right in hand joke blow from research before control 15.1±1.3 in the group, experiment group is 14.3±1.7 did. From research next indicators experience 19.5±1.4 in the control group 17.9±1.5 times in the group organize did. General in the indicator control

group sportsman of his daughters note reached indicators experience group to his daughters relatively low that let's see possible (see Table 1).

Young tennis player girls' left hand joke the blow be able to perform when the level is also determined from research before control in the group note done indicators 13.1 ± 1.9 , experience 12.9 ± 1.9 times in the group organize did. The following indicators are in the study control 15.5 ± 1.7 times in the group, experiment by 17.4 ± 1.1 times in the group that has changed was determined and experience group in daughters this process positive the end with completed was determined.

Movement activities to teach in the process, only education and education duties only not, health is also included adding take will go one common education in subject's wellness task that's all open given not. Movement activities in teaching education have its own task features have. Movement activities to teach another features movement of qualifications system to the body from bringing consists of Only movement activities system only of the student physical readiness determines. But many system options there is they are physical education which to the goal orientation and his sure to the task depends without is selected (Physical education theory and methodology. T.S.Usmonkhodjayev, O'.Tursunov, Kh. Meloboyev . Tashkent 2008. Page 51.).

Tennis ball cut transfer (times) control in the test while note done indicators from research before experience and control in groups in this indicators note done: experiment group tennis player 5.4 ± 1.8 times in daughters. Control group 6.1 ± 1.89 times in daughter's indicators were determined. From research next results while control 7.6 ± 1.64 times in the group, experiment 8.1 ± 1.09 in the group organize did. This is an indicator At the end of experience group in daughters control group to his daughters relatively growth coefficient high the fact that was determined . Results statistics indicator is $P > 0.05$ equal to it happened.

Top-spin shot perform (times) control in the test determined results from research before control group 4.5 ± 1.89 in daughters, experiment in the group and 4.5 ± 1.15 times organize did. From research after this control test on the surface again inspection when transferred control 5.8 ± 1.62 times in the group, experiment in the group and 6.9 ± 1.3 in March indicators was determined. From this apparently standing control in the group growth after research indicator 1.3 equal, experience 2.4 times in the group increased was determined. Results statistics the difference is $P > 0.05$ organize did

The next one controls our test from the left and from the right is a point (triangle). we are young in this tennis player of girls agility quality also determine the indicators opportunity have we will be Of course to indicators basically from research previous results control 6.14 ± 1.02 in the group, experiment 6.2 ± 1.4 in the

group indicators was determined. From research next results while control 6.22 ± 1.18 in the group, experiment in the group and 7.9 ± 1.50 indicators was determined. Received from the results that's it let's see possible experience group sportsman in daughters control group to his daughters relatively high indicators note done was determined.

CONCLUSION

Young table tennis player of girls' technical preparation dynamics determination in order to organize done this research our practice at the end of according to qui to the conclusion our arrival possible:

- Special technical preparation indicators determination for our left and right in the hands joke the blow execution reach through organize done control in the test right in hand joke blow from research before control 15.1 ± 1.3 in the group, experiment group is 14.3 ± 1.7 did. From research next indicators experience 19.5 ± 1.4 in the control group 17.9 ± 1.5 times in the group organize left hand joke the blow be able to perform when the level is also determined from research before control in the group note done indicators 13.1 ± 1.9 , experience 12.9 ± 1.9 times in the group organize did. The following indicators are in the study control 15.5 ± 1.7 times in the group, experiment by 17.4 ± 1.1 times in the group that has changed was determined and experience group in daughters this process positive the end with completed was determined.

Final to the conclusion according to young table tennis player of girls universal and special preparation indicators from us organize done tools using take went training own effect show took. Research during experience group daughters control group to his daughters relatively high the results note reached

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